

Late Presentation of Congenital Incomplete Ileal Stenosis in a Pediatric Patient: A Rare Cause of Intestinal Obstruction

Author: Valentina-Simina Utiu¹

Co-authors: Iulia Malutan¹, Antonia Ioana Bentea¹

Coordinators: Adrian Surd^{2,1}, Kriszta Snakovszki²

Affiliations:

¹ *University of Medicine and Pharmacy Iuliu Hatieganu, Cluj-Napoca, Faculty of General Medicine*

² *County Emergency Clinical Hospital for Children, Pediatric Surgery Department*

Introduction

Congenital ileal stenoses are rare malformations of the small intestine. They represent an incomplete form of intestinal atresia. The intestinal lumen is narrowed but remains permeable, resulting in a delayed clinical presentation.

Case Presentation

A 2-year-and-3-month-old female patient was admitted to the pediatric department with altered general status, fever, and persistent vomiting. The vomiting progressively became bilious, raising suspicion of an obstructive pathology and prompting further investigations. Imaging studies suggested intestinal obstruction, leading to surgical consultation. The definitive diagnosis was established following exploratory laparotomy, which revealed an incomplete ileal diaphragm causing significant luminal stenosis. Surgical management consisted of segmental resection of the affected ileal segment, followed by a diamond-shaped anastomosis. This technique was chosen to ensure adequate luminal widening, minimize the risk of postoperative stricture, and preserve bowel length—an important consideration in pediatric patients. The particularity of this case is its late presentation, as congenital ileal stenoses typically manifest in the neonatal period. The differential diagnosis included malrotation with intermittent volvulus, Meckel's diverticulum, and infectious or inflammatory gastrointestinal disorders.

Conclusion

This case highlights the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion in pediatric patients with persistent or atypical gastrointestinal symptoms, in order to facilitate timely surgical intervention and prevent severe complications associated with delayed diagnosis

Keywords

ileal stenosis, malformations, obstructive pathology